

Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin

D7.3 VIDEOS PRODUCED VER 2

**WP7 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION,
RRI, PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT**

Grant Agreement n°. 101077600

Co-funded by
the European Union

Version History

Ver.	Date	Comments/Changes	Author/Reviewer
0.1	30/07/2024	First draft sent to project partners for review	Silvia Pérez, Beatrice Avagnina, Michelle Perello
0.2	20/08/2024	Draft reviewed by the Coordinator and consortium	Project partners
1.0	30/08/2024	Final draft ready for submission	Silvia Pérez, Beatrice Avagnina, Michelle Perello

Deliverable Information

Project Acronym	AquaWind	
Project Title	Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin	
Call	EMFAF-2021-PIA-FLAGSHIP	
Type of action	EMFAF-PJG EMFAF Project Grants	
Granting authority	The European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA)	
Project Start Date	01/09/2022	
Project Duration	36 months	
Work Package	WP7	
Deliverable	D7.3 Videos produced Ver 2	
Due Date	31/08/2023	
Submission Date	09/08/2023	
Dissemination Level ¹	PU	
Deliverable Responsible	CE	
Type	DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
Version	1	
Status	Final	
Author(s)	Silvia Pérez, Beatrice Avagnina, Michelle Perello	CE
Reviewer(s)	Javier Roo, Rafael Ginés, Daniel Montero Cristina Hernández, Gordon Dalton, Silvia Martin, Carlos Navarro Mónica Quesada, Carmen Muñoz Javier Fernández, Fernando Del Corral Maria Ikhennicheu, Bernardo Kahn Luana Clementino, Paula Bastos Alfred Mormeneo	GOBCAN-ACIISI ULPGC FCPCT PLOCAN CMC EnerOcean Innosea WAVEC CANEXMAR

¹ PU= Public, SEN=Sensitive

Table of Contents

Acronyms & Abbreviations.....	2
Introduction.....	3
1. Animated video	4
1.1 Description and link	4
1.2 Design and format	4
1.3 Storyboard & Script	5
1.4 Dissemination strategy.....	6
2. Storytelling video.....	8
2.1 Description and links	8
2.2 Design and format	8
2.3 Production	9
2.4 Dissemination strategy.....	11
3. Conclusions.....	11

Acronyms & Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EMFAF	European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund
EU	European Union
WP	Work Package

Introduction

The first two promotional videos for the project were created by WP7 leader, Consulta Europa, in collaboration with partners as part of AquaWind's dissemination and communication efforts.

As outlined in the Grant Agreement, AquaWind is expected to produce three promotional videos to support the project's dissemination and communication:

- An animated video to introduce the project's objectives and vision.
- A storytelling video featuring project staff and other stakeholders involved in project activities.
- A demonstration video showcasing the technological and operational aspects of the AquaWind solution.

All videos will be produced in English with subtitles in Spanish, Portuguese, and French—the three languages of the consortium. These videos will be made available on the AquaWind YouTube channel to facilitate wide distribution by sharing the link.

In the present document, Section 1 details the steps to produce the first animated video, and moreover, in Section 2, it is reflected in the elaboration of the second video, gathering partners perspectives and their involvement in the AquaWind project. Deliverable 7.4 Video Produce Ver 3 to be submitted in M36 will outline the production of the demonstration video.

1. Animated video

1.1 Description and link

The first animation video has been released at M12 (see D7.2 Videos Ver 1), with the aim of presenting the overall scope of AquaWind, its objectives, main activities, and results expected from this funding experience. The video has multiple purposes: to convey AquaWind's main messages (as defined in the D7.1 Dissemination & Communication Plan), to help raise public awareness of multi-use platforms and to promote the EU support (specifically of EMFAF) to this type of initiatives.

The video is available on the AquaWind YouTube channel:

EN: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iuBmZY2t4XM>

ES: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vcR_NaD_KB0

PT: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LpE6wkNh89k>

FR: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F_FImNPJ8CE

The English version of the video is also embedded on the homepage of the website.

1.2 Design and format

The video has been designed and developed by CE in coordination with the contracted service provider Help The Studio (cost foreseen in the Grant Agreement). The video makes use of the visual identity and branding of AquaWind. The colours, fonts and official icons of the project are respected in the scenes of the video. The visual identity of the project was created to make it attractive and user-friendly for people of all age. The animation was developed with these guidelines in mind.

As per the Grant Agreement, the videos shall be short and simple. For the first video, a duration of ca. 2 minutes has been agreed to be the best in order to include a comprehensive description of the project whereas keeping the time limited not to lose audience's attention. To facilitate the exploitation of the video in different settings (laptops, social media profiles, smartphones and tablets, conference stands/presentations and exhibition areas), project partners have chosen a hybrid solution including text, voiceover, animations, infographics, etc. Thanks to this mix different audiences in different conditions will be able to understand and enjoy the contents.

The video acknowledges the EU financing at the beginning and at the end of the animation scenes, in line with the guidelines of Art. 17 of the Grant Agreement.

1.3 Storyboard & Script

The production process of the first animation video involved CE crafting the script and collaborating with partners on its development. Following pre-production, graphic elements were designed leading to the creation of an interactive and catchy video. An overview of the storyboard drafted for the video is shown in Table 1, while the script of the video is provided in Table 2.

Table 1. Overview of video’s storyboard

Animated Video Storyboard			

Table 2. Video’s script

	Text
1	AquaWind is a collaborative project co-founded by the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund. The objective is to combine offshore renewable energy production and fish farming, as a first and unique trial on the coast of Gran Canaria in the Canary Islands, Spain.
2	AquaWind relies on an existing floating wind platform named Wind to Power (W2Power). It will be integrated with customised aquaculture cage and remote feeding and monitoring systems to track fish health and welfare and prototype structural behaviour.
3	Pilot tests will be carried out to validate the W2Power performance in combination with the aquaculture operations, also ensuring close environmental and biodiversity monitoring.

4	AquaWind research activities will be crucial to establish a novel route map for regulatory and legal issues for real implementation of multi-use marine projects. Recommendations for policy makers will also be released to support the commercialisation of hybrid wind and aquaculture technologies.
5	The AquaWind solution will be designed and tested following a multi-stakeholder and circular approach to ensure social acceptance and the lowest environmental impact.
6	This inclusive process will engage at regional, national, and European levels: Research and Innovation Stakeholders, Policy Makers, Fishery Communities, and Citizens.
7	With nine partners from Spain, France, and Portugal, the AquaWind consortium brings benefits from its expertise in the sector of marine and aquaculture research, energy systems, environmental impact assessment, project management and communication.
8	The project is a unique innovative action to support the development and uptake of combined marine activities and contributes to the Atlantic Maritime Strategy and the European Green Deal for the sustainable expansion of the Blue Economy.
9	Ultimately, AquaWind will empower business and research in the Atlantic area, by laying the foundation for future multi-use projects in the same area and beyond.

1.4 Dissemination strategy

This video was used as a dissemination tool to promote AquaWind and the consortium both online and offline. It served the purposes of WP7 tasks and WP1 stakeholder engagement activities. First, the video was uploaded to the AquaWind website and YouTube channel. Following the submission of Deliverable 7.2 – Video Produced Ver. 1, the video was disseminated in the second project newsletter, with dedicated promotion through project social media beginning in September 2023. Project partners were encouraged to share this information within their own networks and channels. Additionally, whenever possible, the video was utilized during events and conferences, as shown in Figure 2, either by being included in presentations or played on laptops/screens to illustrate the project's key objectives, procedures, and methodology.

The rationale is that the visual promotion of the project activities and outputs shall create interest around AquaWind and incentive stakeholder groups to get engaged in its dissemination activities and uptake of project results. This facilitates the fact that external audiences might in turn promote the project among their networks, further increasing the number of engaged stakeholders.

Figure 1. Dissemination strategy for video promotion

Figure 2. Utilisation of the video during events

2. Storytelling video

2.1 Description and links

Within the purpose of this document, it is expected to deliver the second video, which has been published on M24, collecting the experience of the partners in the implementation of the project. It also contains the AquaWind project's advisor's testimony.

The objectives of the video are to inform viewers about the work being done by the AquaWind partners, to raise awareness of these projects on various platforms, and to encourage the European Union—more specifically, EMFAF—to support them.

- English version: <https://youtu.be/8kJJl5hAY4>
- Spanish version: <https://youtu.be/CiYERLnmSC4>
- French version: <https://youtu.be/D05cAtbN090>
- Portuguese version: <https://youtu.be/jLHzl0deYKw>

Upon this official release, the video will be also showcased on the project website and promoted through the social medial channels.

2.2 Design and format

In collaboration with the project partners, the video was created by CE, WP7 Leader. AquaWind's visual identity and branding are integrated at both the beginning and end of the video, maintaining consistency with the project's official colours, fonts and icons. The project logo is displayed at all times alongside the lower third, a graphic overlay that provides information about the person speaking. This graphic element has been designed without interfering with the display of the subtitles.

The creation of the video conformed to these guidelines. According to the terms of the Grant Agreement, the videos had to be clear and relatively concise. The second video was determined to be around 5 minutes long, which allowed each partner the necessary time to show their responsibilities in the project.

In addition, in compliance with the guidelines set out in Article 17 of the Grant Agreement, the video acknowledges EU financial support at the beginning and end of the animated scenes.

2.3 Production

The production process began by planning a series of questions to be asked to the partners, who were then interviewed. See questions in Table 3.

Table 3. Interview questions

What is your name and which partner do you represent?
What is your company's track record in this area?
What is your job description and responsibilities under the work package?
What benefits can your company bring by incorporating your expertise into their work package?

Finally, once the filming process was completed, the final script was generated (see table 4). During the post-production phase, the relevant sections of each participant were carefully selected and organised.

Table 4. Script

Text	
GOBCAN - ACIISI	<p>This project is coordinate by the Canary Islands' government, in this case by the ACIISI and this is the first time in Europe that we are going to set up a prototype where we are going to utilise aquaculture and windmill to produce offshore energy together.</p> <p>As I mentioned, it is a pioneer projects that can help to achieve the goals of the Green Deal of the European Union but also that the targets that the Canary Island government has set to implement its circular economy strategy and blue economy strategy, or our smart specialisation strategy and that is also in charge, in this case the Canary Island agency of research and innovation.</p>
EnerOcean	<p>In the Work Package we are leading in the AquaWind project we are leading the way in systems integration for aquaculture on the prototype we already have in Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.</p> <p>We are looking at how to conduct such integration for a successful demonstration, ensuring the adaptation of the fish species to the prototype satisfactorily.</p>
INNOSEA	<p>So, my name is Benardo Kahn. I'm a senior offshore renewable energy engineer at INNOSEA one of the partners of the AquaWind Project.</p> <p>INNOSEA is a company specialising in marine renewable energy. So, we have a lot of experience designing, especially floating wind turbines and marine systems</p> <p>And our role in the Aquawind project is to build a numerical model that combines both the technology from Enerocean for a floating wind turbine, and the aquaculture technology.</p>

WaVEC	<p>Within the AquaWind Project, WavEc is involved in Work Package 1, doing life cycle assessment and also in Work Package 4 dealing with the environmental impact assessment.</p> <p>And for this Work Package, we are looking at the life cycle assessment and, the carbon emissions from the AquaWind prototype.</p> <p>And we are also, doing a baseline characterisation of the project area where the AquaWind prototype will be installed, and we will do in-situ surveys of the operation of the prototype.</p>
CANEXMAR	<p>We participate, as well as in other projects, in the AquaWind project, in which our role is dedicated on how the cage will function as it has a very special and unique structure, and evidently how these animals are going to behave within. Considering that is not only the structure but also is key dedicating an important space for animal welfare.</p>
ULPGC	<p>My name is Rafael Ginés, I am a lecturer of the area of animal production at the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria. My participation in the AquaWind project is linked to the evaluation of the efficiency that we obtain from the fish. They are going to be under rearing conditions, and we have to evaluate how these conditions can influence or not their feed condition, their feed nutrition, their growth and also the health of the animals. We look at the nutritional efficiency, their growth and also their health, as well as the stress they may suffer and how through blood parameters or other indicators of stress we can certify that the performance they do is correct and adequate to their physiology.</p>
CE	<p>My name is Beatrice Avagnina, Managing director of Consulta Europa Projects & Innovation.</p> <p>We lead the Work Package 7 on dissemination and communication, so we are responsible of all the planning and implementation of the promotional activities of the project, and we also support the activities for stakeholder engagement under Work Package 1.</p>
PLOCAN	<p>Work Package 1 and 5 are both freely embedded to the four main objectives of AquaWind one of them, which is the business plan and exploitation plan development linked to Work Package 5 the others that are more related to getting into the market, getting involved and co-create with society and so on, are more related with Work Package 1.</p>
CMC	<p>The participation of the Canary Islands Maritime Cluster in the AquaWind project, implies involving stakeholders at regional, national and European level, prioritising different sectors such as public administrations, academia, business associations and civil society, academia, business associations and civil society.</p> <p>The Canary Islands Maritime Cluster is one of the key actors to facilitate and catalyse the interaction between public and private actors in projects such as AquaWind optimising the use of space through multi-purpose prototypes.</p>
PO	<p>My Name is Sonia Karasavidou the project advisor for AquaWind Project, one of the EMFAF project for the European Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund. The AquaWind</p>

	project is a multi-use project combining both renewable energy and aquaculture, priorities of the European Green Deal.
--	--

2.4 Dissemination strategy

The purpose of AquaWind's second video is to serve as a strategic tool to effectively disseminate the consortium's efforts and achievements. Initially, the video will be featured on the AquaWind website and YouTube channel. A dedicated section will be placed on the website, and all videos produced so far will be embedded in it, and it will be included in the next official project newsletter. Starting in September 2024, targeted promotion will take place across the project's social media platforms by using social ads.

Partners will be encouraged as well to share the video on their own websites and social media channels by highlighting the project's achievements and activities. This approach aims to increase awareness of AquaWind and motivate stakeholders to actively participate in the dissemination and implementation of the project. Additionally, it is anticipated that viewers outside the project will also help spread the word within their own networks.

Conclusions

D7.3 Version 2 is the second of three deliverables focused on creating promotional videos to enhance WP7's dissemination and communication efforts, as well as overall stakeholder engagement, which is also supported by WP1 tasks.

The first and second videos have already been produced and published. The first video was successfully promoted via social media and the website, reaching a wide audience. Consequently, WP7 leaders will now focus on promoting the second video to further increase its visibility and impact. The final video is scheduled for release at the end of the project (M36).

Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Grant Agreement n°. 101077600

Co-funded by
the European Union